

“I’m a strong believer that open access is the way to go for works that have been publicly funded, but there is still a pejorative sense that open access means self-publishing.”

Roger Kain, Professor of Humanities at the School of Advanced Study, University of London

Kain feels that attitudes to open access publishing are slowly changing. This is partly due to the ability for academics to reach a bigger, more diverse audience, the influence that research has when it's disseminated more widely and the higher citations numbers. However, Kain says many scholars in management positions are still of the view that it is an inferior publishing choice and advise early career researchers against it.

But, Kain thinks the momentum for change is building and that the younger generation of academics will move the debate forward.

“The generation of researchers who were early career five or so years ago and are now coming through to the mid-career stage – they are going to carry a very different view of open access to people of my generation.”

Why Kain thinks attitudes to open access publishing are changing

Higher reader numbers

The ability to influence thinking is greater

Higher citation numbers

People believe in equitable access to knowledge

Attitudes to digital publishing are evolving